

2024 OCEAN DECADE CONFERENCE

DECLARATION

Our commitment to support blue education and the Network of the European Blue Schools

2021
2030 United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development

European Blue Schools Declaration Barcelona, 8th April 2024

The EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” projects for the promotion of education on blue sustainability and the protection of marine and freshwater ecosystem

ProBleu, SHORE and BlueLighS
in support of the Network of European Blue Schools

Background

UNESCO's **Education for Sustainable Development (ESD)**¹ framework for 2030 promotes the educational empowerment of society, capable of driving the transformation needed to consciously contribute to the achievement of SDGs for a

¹ <https://www.unesco.org/en/sustainable-development/education>

just and sustainable planet. The integration of **ESD** values and the 17 SDGs and 169 targets into society requires *ad hoc* policies, training and active participation to address the **priority action areas of ESD by 2030**.

Priority action areas ESD² of the UNESCO

- Advancing policy
- Transforming learning environments
- Building capacities of educators
- Empowering and mobilizing youth
- Accelerating local-level actions.

IOC-UNESCO is coordinating the **UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development** targeting **SDG14 (Life below Water)** by responding to 10 challenges³. **Ocean literacy** and, for the educative community, the **blue school curricula**⁴, are key factors to respond to *Challenge 10: Transforming humanity's relationship with the ocean*. In 2023, IOC-UNESCO issued a call to Member States to include **ocean literacy in school curricula by 2025** as part of Education for Sustainable Development (OC Circular Letter No. 2951)⁵. At the One Ocean Summit 2022, the UNESCO Director-General Audrey Azoulay stated “*The international community must make education one of the pillars of its action for the ocean. Because if we want to protect it better, we must teach it better. On the occasion of the One Ocean Summit, I am setting a common goal for our 193 Member States: to include ocean education in school curricula by 2025.*”

In 2022, the **European Commission** published a Communication⁶ focusing on *learning for environmental sustainability* to support education and training systems for the societal change required to meet the sustainable goals set out in EU communications, policies and strategies (e.g. European Green Deal, European Climate Pact, Biodiversity Strategy 2030, New Circular Economy Action Plan, etc). The **EU Mission “Restore our ocean and waters by 2030”**, hereafter EU Mission, captured the IOC-UNESCO’s objective in a call for projects⁷ to consolidate and expand the **Network of European Blue Schools** in the European Union and associated countries. The EU Mission promoted the empowerment of the education community to implement actions of **ocean literacy** in the framework of Education for

² <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374802>

³ <https://oceandecade.org/>

⁴ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000380544>

⁵ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000386655>

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022DC0011>

⁷ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/HORIZON_HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-08/en

Sustainability to contribute to the expansion of the Network of European Blue Schools. The collaboration and commitment to strengthen blue education in support of societal transformation in Europe through the Network of European Blue Schools has been consolidated in the **Charter for Blue Education in Europe** (Lisboa 2022)⁸, which sets out 10 objectives for **blue education in Europe**.

The Projects

The projects **ProBleu**, **SHORE**, and **BlueLightS** are funded in the Framework of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean & Waters.” They result from the mission's commitment to ocean literacy. These projects are focused on digital tools, student empowerment, and expanding the Network of European Blue Schools through initiatives for freshwaters and seas.

ProBleu engages school communities in the "Restoring Ocean and Waters" Mission. The project aims to expand the Network of European Blue Schools, promote citizen science, and offer innovative educational materials and funding opportunities. Blue Schools encourage student engagement with ocean and freshwater topics, nurturing a sense of responsibility.

SHORE strives to increase ocean literacy by engaging students and teachers to implement the objectives of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters” through activities and collaborative projects in schools. SHORE also guides educators and provides students with the right skills and knowledge to become eco-citizens.

BlueLightS empowers European children and youth to enhance resilience and sustainability in rivers and seas through collaborative school projects, fostering dialogue between education communities, and piloting innovative changes in educational systems. The initiative aligns with the EU's goal of restoring oceans and waters by 2030, serving as a crucial component for its success.

Common Principles

This **Declaration - Our commitment to support blue education and the Network of the European Blue Schools** has been presented at the UN **Ocean Decade Conference 2024** (Barcelona) in the framework of the dialogue called *European*

⁸ https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-08/charter_for_blue_education_final_final.pdf

Blue Schools, toward the ambitious target of the Mission Ocean & Waters and UNESCO about ocean literacy in the school curricula, a dialogue promoted by the EU funded ProBleu, SHORE and BlueLightS Consortia coalition under the EU Mission Ocean and waters toward the Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) goal.

The collective discussion has helped identify five principles of the collaborative approach set by the three projects to support the achievement of ESD in line with national, European and international agreements on blue education within the EU Mission.

EU Mission Ocean and Waters funded projects ProBleu, SHORE, and BlueLightS commit to support ocean literacy and blue education through **five key principles**.

1. Collaborate

By collaborating across different geographical areas, the projects will best combine resources, expertise and networks, to collectively and more effectively achieve their common goals. This includes supporting the educational community through resources, services and tools that will enable schools to implement blue challenge initiatives. An informal **core group** of representatives of the three projects and of the Network of European Blue Schools (NEBS) Secretariat has been established, and will work to set up collaboration in relation to:

- **Calls** for blue education proposals by schools;
- The setting up of a European Blue Education **Community of Practice**;
- The organisation of Blue School Hubs that will provide **support and help** to schools and the education communities in different countries;
- The organisation of activities (communication, events...) that will enhance the **visibility** of blue education in Europe.

2. Enhance

Supporting the **formal and informal education community** in implementing **blue education**, leading society towards transformative changes in our relationship with the ocean and waters, and integrating concepts of sustainability and ocean literacy by providing a resource base with clear added value and relevance is a common ambition of the three projects. This cooperation will support the implementation of **SDG 14** of the Agenda 2030 as well as the achievement of the objectives of **CH10** of the Ocean Decade of IOC-UNESCO.

3. Connect

The projects build on, reinforce, and consolidate current priorities and topics at international, European and national levels. They will support the dialogue among interested parties and actors, focusing on sustainability, equity, open schooling, cooperation, twinning between different educational institutions, student engagement, participation, project-based learning and 21st-century skills development. The **direct engagement of schools, teachers and students** in the co-design and implementation of blue education activities is a priority for the three EU projects as well as for the exchange of best practices and knowledge.

4. Contribute

The projects support the **integration** of the blue **into education policies and strategies** from the local to the national levels by facilitating the institutional integration of blue literacy concepts into the school curricula, training for teachers or incentives guiding the professional development of education professionals. The three EU projects nourish the discussions by participating in political roundtables and dialogues on the implementation of new educational approaches related to the achievement of the **ESD**, as well as upholding and promoting international initiatives already underway.

5. Communicate

The projects are committed to enhancing the **visibility of blue education** and of the **Network of European Blue Schools**, in line with the **Charter for Blue Education in Europe**. By working together to mobilise the education community and engage citizens and elected representatives, they will **support the achievement of the ambition and objectives of the EU Mission Ocean & Waters**.

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REVOLVE

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European Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030

EU MISSIONS

RESTORE OUR OCEAN & WATERS